

Active Learning for Introduction to Engineering Courses: the University of Brasilia Production Engineering Case as Support for a Unifying Proposal Centred on PBL & Flipped Classroom

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060737>

Abstract

This paper describes the application of active learning methodologies in the Introduction to Production Engineering (IEPR) course at the University of Brasília since 2018, highlighting the use of Problem/Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Flipped Classroom. IEPR, centered on workshops, emphasizes real-life problems and opportunities, including projects related to sustainable, innovative, privacy-protecting, and business-oriented systems. This approach has allowed the IEPR to be categorized as an extension activity. Four anchors support the IEPR workshops: Reality (A1), involving megathemes and corresponding stakeholders with real problems and opportunities, as well as scientific publications; Methodology (A2), which considers regulated professional sectors, academic evaluation, and areas of interest for professional associations, developing teamwork through PBL and Flipped Classroom to understand engineering with a focus on Production Engineering, prepare educational materials (graphics, texts, posters, videos), deliver lectures, formulate questions to assess learning, interact with stakeholders and competent entities, perform bibliometric searches, consolidate teamwork in video format, and report lessons learned; Specific Contents (A3), covering topics from the Production Engineering Program at UnB, Introduction to Systems Approach, Learning and Teaching Organization as a Purposeful System, Legislation and Regulations: Professional Attributions, Academic, Professional Association Interests, Technical and Scientific Writing; and Other Anchors (A4), including other issues, essentially other courses, with interest in IEPR topics. The proposal is to use the IEPR framework as a template to create preliminary versions of other Introduction to Engineering courses with the same structure. From a broader perspective, the IEPR framework may serve as the basis for establishing an Introduction to Engineering Course (IENG) encompassing Production Engineering and other undergraduate engineering programs at the Faculty of Technology at UnB.

Keywords: Active Learning, Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Flipped Classroom, Introduction to Engineering, Production Engineering

1 Introduction

This paper addresses the application of active learning methodologies, specifically Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and Flipped Classroom, in the Introduction to Production Engineering (IEPR) course of the Undergraduate Program in Production Engineering at the Faculty of Technology of the University of Brasília (PEUP-UnB) since 2018. Additionally, it presents a proposal for adapting the framework used in IEPR to other Introduction to Engineering courses under the umbrella of active learning approaches.

In addition to PBL, IEPR includes the Flipped Classroom as an active learning tool to build the Content Integration Workshop (CIW-IEPR), which constitutes the fundamental working environment for teamwork. Four anchors (A1 to A4) support the CIW-IEPR: A1-REALITY: real-life megathemes for teamwork (focused on

sustainability, innovation, privacy, and decision-making adjusted to risk), including interaction with stakeholders and/or people and entities with competencies on the megatheme; A2-METHODOLOGY: student project groups (three to five participants) develop teamwork using PBL and Flipped Classroom active learning tools, focusing on Anchor A1 megathemes; A3-SPECIFIC CONTENTS related to the megathemes to support teamwork sessions; and A4-OTHER ANCHORS: especially other courses with interest in IEPR project topics.

The remainder of the paper is divided into three chapters. Chapter 2 outlines IEPR in terms of the specific contents for teamwork in Content Integration Workshops (CIW-IEPR) focusing on Megatheme1: Understanding Production Engineering in Brazil, including individual questionnaires on it; and Megatheme2: Applications of Production Engineering on components of solid waste systems, including bibliometric searches and/or interactions with stakeholders, persons, and entities with competencies on the subject.

Chapter 3 details the four anchors of the Content Integration Workshop (CIW-IEPR): A1-Reality: Megatheme1 and Megatheme2, including orientation on technical and scientific writing; A2-Methodology: PBL and Flipped Classroom; A3-Specific contents: all those outlined in Chapter 2; and A4-Other anchors: emphasis on other courses, both inside and outside the Faculty of Technology, with interest in IEPR project topics.

Chapter 4 summarizes the material presented in Chapters 2 and 3, proposing an Introduction to Engineering course that merges IEPR and other Introduction to Engineering courses at FT/UnB, under the supervision of both the Faculty of Technology Direction (FTD) and the Faculty of Technology Extension Coordination (EC/FT), with the details of each Engineering Undergraduate Program continuing under the responsibility of the corresponding Academic Coordination. This includes: 1-The adoption of active learning approaches to other Introduction to Engineering courses, emphasizing PBL and Flipped Classroom as a requirement; 2-An initial week Opening Ceremony, including: a-FTD Welcome to freshmen of the Faculty of Technology Engineering Undergraduate Programs (EUP/FT); b-Presentation of the EUP/FT by both EC/FT (presenting the extension activities involved) and the corresponding Academic Coordinator of each Engineering Undergraduate Program (detailing the program under his/her responsibility); 3-A last week Closing Ceremony: a-Summary of the teamwork results, presented by both FTD and EC/FT; b-Presentation of the best teamwork results in terms of consolidated videos; c-Possible comments on the project results achieved by stakeholders and/or persons and entities with competence on the subjects; d-Recognition of the best teamwork results, with certificates issued by FTD and/or EC/FT.

2 The Introduction to Production Engineering (IEPR) course at FT/UnB

The Introduction to Production Engineering (IEPR) course, a PEUP-UnB required first-semester course, is designed not only to understand Production Engineering as a profession in Brazil but also to explore sustainable, innovative, privacy-protecting applications with decision-making adjusted to risk. To achieve this, IEPR adapts the Project-Based Learning (PBL) approach used in the Production Systems Projects courses (PSP1 to PSP8), which begin in the fourth semester of PEUP-UnB.

IEPR extensively uses two active learning approaches: 1) PBL (Christie & de Graaff, 2017; Edström & Kolmos, 2014; de Graaff & Kolmos, 2007; de Graaff & Kolmos, 2003; Kolmos, 2009; Lima et al., 2017; Lima et al., 2007) and 2) Flipped Classroom (Derek BOK Center, 2024).

After summarizing the competencies of an engineer in terms of knowledge ("intelligence"), skills, and attitudes, the course includes a description of the PEUP-UnB components (Lima et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2013; Silva et al., 2016; Silva et al., 2017): Mathematics, Physics, Information Systems, Technology, Production Engineering Basics, Advanced Production Engineering contents, related elective contents, great themes, synthesis, integration and

entrepreneurship, supervised internship, graduation projects 1 and 2, complementary activities, and free choice of elective contents.

Next, the course introduces systems approach (Ackoff, 1974; Ackoff & Gharajedaghi, 2011; Bunge, 1989; Checkland, 1981; Ögden & Richards, 1923; Jaguaribe, 1973; PMBOK 6, 2017; Tolk, 2010; Turnitsa et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2013; Hamasaki et al., 2022), covering the semiotic trapezoid, categorization according to cardinal points, modeling attributes, open system description, open systems in regard to the purpose of the whole and its parts, and society models.

The course considers learning and teaching organization as purposeful social system (Garavan, 1997; Pedlar et al., 1991; Lourenço et al., 2023; Romme & Arjen, 1999), oriented to sustainability, innovation, privacy protection, and decisions adjusted to risk (United Nations 2030 Agenda, 2015; OECD/Eurostat, 2018; Brazilian General Data Protection Law – LGPD, 2020; GDPR, 2016; Fair Information Practice Principles – FIPPs, 2016; FIPPs at Berkeley, 2024). It is emphasized the excellence in multiple learning and teaching levels (Wasdell, 1993: efficiency, efficacy, eminence, effectiveness), the increasing degrees of organizational evolution (existence, experience, emergence, evidence), and considered the competing values framework ("complementary organizational values") (Cameron, 2024; Robert E. Quinn's Competing Values Framework, 2024; Tianyuan Yu et al., 2009).

The course summarizes legislation and regulations regarding professional attributions (Brazilian Engineering and Agronomy Federal Council – CONFEA: CONFEA, 2005a; CONFEA, 2005b; CONFEA, 2013; CONFEA, 2016) and academic matters (Ministry of Education – MEC: MEC, 2019; MEC, 2023a; MEC, 2023b; MEC, 2023c), complemented by the areas of interest of both, the Brazilian Production Engineering Association (ABEPRO) and the Institute of Industrial and Systems Engineers (IISE).

Given that most teamwork activities result in written materials required to be presented in both Portuguese and English, it is mandatory to introduce the basic concepts of technical and scientific writing in both languages (Machado, 2024; Gonçalves et al., 2023; Perelman et al., 2024). To consolidate part of the conceptual material, students must answer questionnaires on sustainability, innovation, and privacy protection before starting teamwork activities. Figure 1 synthesizes the IEPR description.

Figure 1. Synthesis of IEPR Description

3 The IEPR Content Integration Workshop (CIW-IEPR)

PBL and Flipped Classroom are the active learning tool used to build the IEPR Content Integration Workshop (CIW-IEPR), fundamental working environment for teamwork. As shown in Figure 2 (adaptation of Figure 7.4 of Guerra et al., 2017), four Anchors (A1 to A4) supports CIW-IEPR:

A1-REALITY: megathemes and their stakeholders and/or people and/or entities with competence in them:

- Megatheme1: Understanding Production Engineering in Brazil under three perspectives: 1) six regulated professional sectors; 2) sixteen academic evaluation contents; and 3) ten ABEPRO and fourteen IISE professional association interest areas.
- Megatheme2: Considering the PRE understanding acquired through Megatheme1, identify and characterize PRE applications in components of Solid Waste Systems, categorized according to PRE CONFEA sectors.

Figure 2. Content Integration Workshop (CIW-IEPR) for IEPR Teamworking

A2-METHODOLOGY: Student project groups (minimum of 3 and maximum of 5 participants) develop teamwork using Flipped Classroom and PBL related to Megatheme1 and Megatheme2 of Anchor A1:

- **Megatheme1:** Considering the 1) six regulated professional sectors; 2) sixteen academic evaluation contents; and 3) ten ABEPRO and fourteen IISE interest areas of professional associations, the teamwork (i) understand engineering, with an emphasis on Production Engineering; (ii) prepare educational material (graphics, texts, posters, videos); (iii) present a lecture on one of the six PRE CONFEA regulated professional sectors; (iv) formulate questions for a questionnaire to assess the learning of the session content; (v) interact with stakeholders and/or competent people and entities related to Megatheme1; (vi) performs bibliometric searches on Megatheme1 subjects; and (vii) reports lessons learned. Table 1 shows the components of the three Production Engineering perspectives: Professional Attributions, Academic Formation and Assessment, and Areas of Interest of Professional Associations.

Table 1. Components of Three Production Engineering Perspectives in Brazil

PERSPECTIVES FOR UNDERSTANDING PRODUCTION ENGINEERING IN BRAZIL			
PROFESSIONAL ATTRIBUTIONS CONFEA/CREAS 6 SECTORS	ACADEMIC FORMATION&ASSESSMENT MEC/CNE/CES/INEP/ENADE 2023 16 "PROFESSIONALIZING" CONTENTS	AREAS OF INTEREST OF PROFESSIONAL ASSOCIATIONS	
		BRAZILIAN PRODUCTION ENGINEERING ASSOCIATION (ABEPRO): 10 AREAS	INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL AND SYSTEMS ENGINEERS (IISE): 14 AREAS
1.3.21-ENGINEERING OF PHYSICAL PRODUCTION PROCESSES	EPR04-ENGINEERING ECONOMY	AB01-OPERATION ENGINEERING AND PRODUCTION PROCESSES	1-WORK DESIGN&MEASUREMENT
1.3.22-QUALITY ENGINEERING	EPR05-PRODUCT ENGINEERING	AB02-SUPPLY CHAIN	2-OPERATIONS RESEARCH&ANALYSIS
1.3.23-ERGONOMICS	EPR06-WORK ENGINEERING	AB03-OPERATIONS RESEARCH	3-ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ANALYSIS
1.3.24-OPERATIONS RESEARCH	EPR07-ERGONOMICS	AB04-QUALITY ENGINEERING	4-FACILITIES ENGINEERING&ENERGY MANAGEMENT
1.3.25-ORGANIZATIONAL ENGINEERING	EPR08-STATISTICS	AB05-PRODUCT ENGINEERING	5- QUALITY&RELIABILITY ENGINEERING
1.3.26-ENGINEERING ECONOMY	EPR09-STRATEGY AND ORGANIZATION	AB06-ORGANIZATIONAL ENGINEERING	6-ERGONOMICS&HUMAN FACTORS
	EPR10-GRAPHICAL EXPRESSION	AB07-ENGINEERING ECONOMY	7-OPERATIONS ENGINEERING&MANAGEMENT
	EPR13-ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT	AB08-WORK ENGINEERING	8-SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT
	EPR14-PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT	AB09-SUSTAINABILITY ENGINEERING	9-ENGINEERING MANAGEMENT
	EPR15-HYGIENE AND SAFETY AT WORK	AB10-EDUCATION IN PRODUCTION ENGINEERING	10-SAFETY
	EPR16-LOGISTICS		11-INFORMATION ENGINEERING
	EPR19-OPERATIONS RESEARCH		12-DESIGN&MANUFACTURING ENGINEERING
	EPR20-MANUFACTURING PROCESSES		13-PRODUCT DESIGN&DEVELOPMENT
	EPR21-QUALITY		14-SYSTEM DESIGN&ENGINEERING
	EPR23-SYSTEMS SIMULATION		
	EPR24-INFORMATION SYSTEMS		

- Megatheme2:** Figure 3 shows a consolidated view of the Basic Sanitation System in terms of **1) Portfolios** (Water=W1, Sewage=S, Drainage and Rainwater=D, Waste=W2); **2) Programs** (Waste=W2: Prevention=P, Reduction=R1, Reuse=R2, Recycling=R3, Disposal in Sanitary Landfills=D); and **3) Projects/Applications** (Solid Waste Recovery via Cooperatives of Waste Pickers: R2-Reuse and R3-Recycling; Waste Disposal in Sanitary Landfills; and Product Engineering, with a focus on Prevention=P and Reduction=R1). Focusing on the components of Solid Waste Systems highlighted by dotted red lines in Figure 3, and taking into account the understanding of Production Engineering acquired through Megatheme1, the student groups: (i) perform bibliometric searches on Production Engineering applications (related to one of the six PRE CONFEA sectors) that are sustainable, innovative, privacy-protecting, with decisions adjusted to risk; (ii) interact with stakeholders and/or competent people and entities; (iii) prepare graphics, texts, posters and videos related to the components of Solid Waste Systems; (iv) present the results of teamwork to the class.

Figure 3. Basic Sanitation System: Focus on Solid Waste

A3-SPECIFIC CONTENTS: to be used during teamwork sessions, as detailed in Figure 2.

A4-OTHER ANCHORS: Enrichment by other contents, especially those brought by other courses.

The integration of these megathemes by the class as a team is essential for the preparation and participation in the IEPR closing event, demonstrating the collective understanding and application of the course concepts. The focus on both megathemes allows students to synthesize their knowledge of Production Engineering in Brazil and apply it to real-world scenarios, including sustainable, innovative, and privacy-protecting

applications with decisions adjusted to risk. The approximate results achieved by IEPR during the 12-semester period since 2018 are the following:

- Students: 600,
- Student groups: 150,
- Group reports: 300,
- Closing tele-events: 12,
- 900 questions formulated by IEPR students related to the understanding of PRE in Brazil,
- Tutors and Monitors: 60, responsible for 1-Bibliometry tutorial, 2-Teamwork guidance, and 3-Preliminary assessment of group reports.

4 Proposal for Merging Introduction to Engineering Courses at FT/UnB

Figures 1, 2, and 3 can serve as templates for creating preliminary versions of other Introduction to Engineering courses with the same framework by substituting the words written in RED for the corresponding words of other Engineering Programs. For instance, replacing "PRODUCTION ENGINEERING" (PRE) by "MECHATRONICS ENGINEERING" (MTE), and all text related to the focus of Megatheme2 by a subject of interest defined by the Mechatronics Engineering Academic Coordination. It follows a proposed general extended syllabus for an Introduction to Engineering Course (**IENG**) encompassing Production Engineering and other Undergraduate Engineering Programs at FT/UnB.

Welcome Ceremony: The welcome ceremony will include a general scope of Engineering with a particular emphasis on those Engineering fields with undergraduate programs at the Faculty of Technology (FT) of the University of Brasília (UnB). This segment will be presented by the FT Direction (FTD). Extension activities involved in IENG will be presented by the Extension Coordination of the Faculty of Technology of UnB (EC-FT/UnB). Additionally, there will be a summary of the Engineering Undergraduate Programs included in IENG, presented by the corresponding Academic Coordination.

Contents (Responsibility of the Corresponding Academic Coordination): This section includes an introduction to the systems approach and learning and teaching organization as a purposeful social system, oriented towards sustainability, innovation, privacy protection, and decisions adjusted to risk. It also covers excellence in multiple learning and teaching levels (EX1: Efficiency, EX2: Efficacy, EX3: Eminence, EX4: Effectiveness), increasing degrees of organizational evolution (EV1: Existence, EV2: Experience, EV3: Emergence, EV4: Evidence), and considering complementary organizational values (C1: Create, C2: Collaborate, C3: Control, C4: Compete). There will be a summary of the legislation and regulations regarding professional attributions (Brazilian Engineering and Agronomy Federal Council – CONFEA and Brazilian Engineering and Agronomy Regional Councils – CREAs) and academic matters (Ministry of Education – MEC/National Education Council – CNE/Superior Education Chamber – CES/National Pedagogical Studies Institute – INEP/National Student Performance Exam – ENADE), complemented by a brief explanation of the areas of interest of a Brazilian Professional Association representing the Engineering field (e.g., the Brazilian Production Engineering Association – ABEPRO). Technical and scientific writing will also be covered in both Portuguese (ABNT Norms, as in UFPR) and English (Mayfield Handbook of Technical Scientific Writing, as in MIT).

Teamwork: Teamwork will involve the preparation and presentation of a lecture focusing on one of the CONFEA Technical Sectors of the corresponding Engineering field, including the formulation of questions to assess the understanding of the lecture content. It will also involve carrying out bibliometric searches on the understanding of the corresponding Engineering field, as well as sustainable, innovative, privacy-protecting applications with decisions adjusted to risk, associated with the subject of interest defined by the Academic

Coordination for Megatheme 2. Preparation and participation in the closing tele-event will aim to show the organization of the whole class as one team.

Closing Ceremony: The closing ceremony will include a summary of the IENG teamwork results, presented by FTD. Extension activities developed in IENG will be presented by EC-FT/UnB. The best teamwork results for each of the participating Engineering Programs will be presented in terms of consolidated videos. There will also be comments from stakeholders and/or other persons, groups, and entities interested in IENG, and recognition of the best teamwork results, with certificates issued by FTD and/or EC-FT/UnB.

5 Conclusion

Since 2018, this model has been implemented in the Production Engineering course at the University of Brasília (UnB), and it has already shown positive results with graduated students. The primary objective of this paper was to present a proposal for a model that can be adapted to other Introduction to Engineering courses using the same framework. Figures 1, 2, and 3 serve as templates for creating preliminary versions of these courses. From a broader perspective, the IEPR framework may serve as the foundation for establishing an Introduction to Engineering Course (IENG) that encompasses Production Engineering and potentially all other Undergraduate Engineering Programs at FT/UnB. This would be done under the coordination of the Faculty of Technology Direction (FTD) and the Extension Coordination of the Faculty of Technology (EC-FT/UnB), ensuring a cohesive and comprehensive approach to engineering education at the university. Although the model has shown promising results in the Production Engineering course, further research is needed to evaluate its effectiveness across different engineering disciplines. Future studies should focus on the adaptation process, evaluating the outcomes, and identifying best practices for broader implementation.

Acknowledgements

This work was partially developed in the context of project 2023-1-DK01-KA220-HED-00165709, “EGALITARIAN - Education, Digitalisation and Collaboration for Sustainability” which has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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